

CYCLOPES - Fighting Cybercrime – Law Enforcement Practitioners’ Network

Deliverable 4.4 3rd Annual standardisation recommendations Public

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Summary

Deliverable D4.4 was developed in Task 4.3 and details recommendations for standardisation in the field of

- “Cryptocurrency as a facilitator for Cybercrime” (see Section 1),
- “Internet of Things Devices” (see Section 2), and
- “Investigations involving Cloud Services” (see Section 3)

based on needs, experiences and expectations expressed by Law Enforcement Agencies (LEAs) during dedicated practitioners’ workshops in the framework of CYCLOPES WP 2, Identification of practitioners’ capabilities, gaps and requirements.

Additionally, this deliverable provides the follow-up of previous recommendations for standardisation (see Section 4).

Introduction

WP4 Overview

Work Package 4 is divided in the following tasks:

Task 4.1 WP4 Terms of Reference

The aim of this task is to develop WP4’s Terms of Reference, defining in detail:

- The standardisation state of the art in the area of fighting cybercrime: identifying relevant CEN/CENELEC/ISO technical committees, related projects and other national and international activities. Determining the relevant stakeholders and highlighting persons in law enforcement interested in the topic (within consortium partners and the wider CYCLOPES LEA Community). Agreeing on the structure for WP4 standardisation reports.
- Innovation uptake state of the art in the security area: identification of current legal regulations, frameworks and best practices providing LEAs with an effective procurement approach for innovative solutions. Recognising the relevant stakeholders and persons in law enforcement that are interested in this topic.

Deliverable D4.1 contains WP4’s Terms of Reference.

Task 4.2 Standardisation recommendations

Partners involved in this task will participate in the practitioners’ workshops, facilitating one-hour discussions dedicated to previous experiences related to standardisation, expectations, priorities and needs in this area. Combining information gathered from the practitioners’ workshops with ongoing analyses of current and forthcoming works conducted by standardisation bodies will be a baseline for the series of annual reports on standardisation recommendations.

Task 4.3 Annual standardisation workshops

Based on information gathered within task 4.2, CYCLOPES will choose at least one topic, which will be further elaborated during a dedicated yearly workshop. Workshops will be organised independently, or in cooperation with particular technical committees' workshops or conferences. The ambition is to promote standardisation as an effective tool in the fight against cybercrime, while exploring the opportunities to streamline processes and procedures that will maintain efficacy and maximise effectiveness. The inputs gathered from the participants during the yearly workshops will be summarised in the reports that constitute the Deliverables 4.2 to D4.6, Annual standardisation recommendations.

Task 4.4 Innovation uptake recommendations

Innovation uptake is a process, starting from the elicitation of the specific needs of users, utilising the most appropriate innovation procurement model for the demand, and then ensuring the greatest impact of a new innovation – with a specific testing, validation and improvement loop. In this task, we will gather and collate existing frameworks, best practices and guidelines for innovation uptake in the Security area, along with the outcomes in WP3. Other activities in this task include the assimilation of key aspects of the materials gathered; providing recommendations for LEAs on the most congruent approach for cybercrime innovation uptake.

WP4 Objectives

WP4 has two main objectives:

- 1) to identify priorities related to fighting cybercrime which require more standardisation;
- 2) to develop recommendations, facilitating and fostering cybercrime innovation uptake in LEAs.

WP4 will contribute to the overall CYCLOPES project Objective 4:

Ob 4. To indicate priorities regarding domains requiring standardisation and innovation uptake

4.1 To define a roadmap with recommendations for standardisation based on the needs and possibilities for the standardisation of tools, procedures and trainings related to fighting cybercrime.

Related KPI: An annual report providing recommendations for standardisation will be delivered. The composition of these reports will create a standardisation roadmap.

Methods of measurement: Tasks 4.2, 4.3 and deliverables D4.2 to D4.6.

4.2 To provide a roadmap with recommendations to LEAs for the effective (also cost-efficient) innovation uptake, based on identified experiences, best practices, legal regulations and EU/national financial and organisational incentives for innovation uptake.

Related KPI: One annual report with recommendations on innovation uptake will be prepared. The innovation uptake roadmap will be a composition of all 5 reports.

Methods of measurement: Task 4.4 and deliverables D4.7 to D4.11.

WP4 Deliverables

D4.1 WP4 Terms of Reference (M06)

D4.2 1st Annual standardisation recommendations (M12)

D4.3 2nd Annual standardisation recommendations (M24)

D4.4 3rd Annual standardisation recommendations (M36)

D4.5 4th Annual standardisation recommendations (M48)

D4.6 5th Annual standardisation recommendations (M60)

D4.7 1st Annual innovation uptake recommendations (M12)

D4.8 2nd Annual innovation uptake recommendations (M24)

D4.9 3rd Annual innovation uptake recommendations (M36)

D4.10 4th Annual innovation uptake recommendations (M48)

D4.11 5th Annual innovation uptake recommendations (M60)

WP4 Partners

CYCLOPES partners participating in the individual tasks of WP4 are presented in table 1.

Table 1 CYCLOPES partners' involvement in WP4 tasks

Partner Acronym	Partner full name	T4.1 WP4 Terms of Reference	T4.2 Standardisation recommendations	T4.3 Annual standardisation workshops	T4.4 Innovation uptake recommendations
ASI	Austrian Standards International	X	X	X	
BFP	Police Federale Belge			X	X
CPEB	College of Policing Limited, United Kingdom	X	X	X	X
GDCOC	Glavna Direktsia Borba S Organiziranata Prestupnost			X	X
GUCI	Ministerio del Interior, Spain			X	X
HO	Home Office United Kingdom			X	X
IANUS	IANUS Consulting Ltd.				X
KWPG	Provincial Police Headquarters in Gdansk			X	X
MPF	Malta Police Force			X	X
MUP	Ministry of Interior, Croatia			X	X
NPN	The National Police of the Netherlands			X	X
PPHS	Polish Platform for Homeland Security	X	X	X	X
SPA	Polismyndigheten Swedish Policy Authority	X	X	X	X
SPLV	Iekšlietu Ministrijas Valsts Policija State Police of the Ministry of Interior, Latvia			X	X
ZITIS	Zentrale Stelle für Informationstechnik im Sicherheitsbereich	X	X	X	X

Participation of CYCLOPES partners in standardisation communities

In February 2024 an online questionnaire (see Figure 1) was circulated to CYCLOPES partners to gain information, who participates in which standardisation committees.

Figure 1 Questionnaire for the participation of CYCLOPES partners in standardisation communities

For completing the questionnaire CYCLOPES partners were instructed to also consult colleagues from other departments in their organization.

CYCLOPES partners were also made aware, that the participation in Technical Committees of CEN, CENELEC, ISO and IEC follows the “national delegation principle” (see Annex A: Standardisation overview), e.g. in Germany ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27 is mirrored by the DIN NA 043-04-27 AA, Informationssicherheit, Cybersicherheit und Datenschutz; in Belgium ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27 is mirrored by AGORIA-ICT and in The Netherlands by NEN’s normcommissie ‘Cybersecurity & Privacy’. In other standardisation bodies like ETSI, individual experts and organizations participate directly without being nominated by a National Standardisation Body.

Eight partners answered this questionnaire, including partners representing Law Enforcement Agencies. The standardisation communities in which they participate are shown in Figure 2 with the number of CYCLOPES partners.

D4.4 3rd Annual standardisation recommendations

Figure 2 Participation of CYCLOPES in standardisation communities

It is clear that CYCLOPES partners are already contributing to standardisation activities and are well-placed to make valuable recommendations.

Combined with the expertise of other CYCLOPES stakeholders, the project can make efficient and effective standardisation recommendations.

1. Selected Topic: Cryptocurrency as a facilitator for Cybercrime

On the 7th and 8th of December 2022, WP2 organised a practitioner workshop on the topic of Cryptocurrency as a facilitator of cybercrime.

The standardisation landscape of Cryptocurrency, produced by this WP2 activity, is as follows:

- ISO/TC 68/SC 2/WG 17, Security aspects of digital currencies

ISO Technical Specification ISO/TS 23526, *Security aspects for digital currencies*, was elaborated in this working group. This Standardisation deliverable, which was published in 2023, describes the management of cryptographic keys in a blockchain, or distributed system used in the financial sector. The objective of the ISO/TS is to consider the impact of different types of key management processes that are required for PKI implementations in Blockchain and Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT) projects.

- ISO/TC 68/SC 8/WG 3, Digital Token Identifier – DTI

ISO 24165-1:2021, *Digital token identifier (DTI) – Registration, assignment and structure – Part 1: Method for registration and assignment*, was elaborated in this working group. This ISO Standard defines the assignment and generation of a random, unique, fixed-length identifier for digital tokens in response to a request for registration that conforms to specified application guidelines. Part 1 of ISO 24165 is complemented by ISO 24165-2:2021, *Digital token identifier (DTI) – Registration, assignment and structure – Part 2: Data elements for registration*. This defines the data elements included in the registry record and used to establish the 1:1 relationship between a digital token and the identifier, assigned according to the method in ISO 24165-1.

The standard is implemented by Etrading Software, the registration authority¹ of ISO 24165, which issues digital token identifiers and maintains them in a publicly accessible central register on their website.

- ISO/TC 307, Blockchain and distributed ledger technologies

This ISO Technical Committee has an Advisory Group AG 3 on digital currencies and a Joint Working Group JWG 4 with ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27 on security, privacy and identity for Blockchain and DLT.

- The multi-part ISO Standard ISO 20022, *Financial services – Universal financial industry message scheme*, is also relevant. But it should be noted that while the financial institutions and payment systems have adopted, or are in the process of adopting, ISO 20022 standards for their operations, cryptocurrencies generally operate outside the traditional financial system and do not adhere to the ISO 20022 standard by default. Cryptocurrencies have their own protocols and messaging formats that are specific to each cryptocurrency's blockchain network. Cryptocurrencies can be transported as data content in the ISO 20022 messages but are not validated. Today fiat currencies (EUR, USD, etc...) are used in the messages and validated against ISO

¹ See https://www.iso.org/maintenance_agencies.html

4217; but cryptocurrencies validation will be implemented in future version of the ISO 20022 messages.

Partners of Task 4.2 participated in the WP2 Workshop on Cryptocurrency as a facilitator of cybercrime and collected the following practitioner requirements. These needs were assessed regarding how they can be met by standardisation.

- 1) Cryptocurrencies are used to facilitate drug trafficking (and other drug related crimes); theft; other crimes involving the need to hide identity, hide the origin of the money or hide large amounts of money. Some practitioners use commercial digital forensics tools to detect the presence of artifacts. The quality assurance of such tools is unclear and standardised **criteria for tools** are often absent.
- 2) There would appear to be a lack of a **standardised methodology for cryptocurrency seizure**. Typically, when crypto wallets/keys are recovered, solutions are required on site to seize. This includes the needs for
 - standardisation in terms of practice, policy and procedure(s),
 - standard(s) for at-scene digital forensics,
 - standardised data exchange format.

The need for standardised criteria for digital forensics tools, including methods for the validation and verification of these tools, is addressed in more detail in Subsection 3.3.1.

An in-depth analysis of the other needs showed that these topics are mostly covered in existing standards coming from ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27. The applicability of those standards to investigation process classes and activities is presented in Figure 3.

The International Standard ISO/IEC 27035, *Information technology — Information security incident management*, with its three parts can be useful for answering the needs for a **standardised data exchange format** together with CASE (Cyber-investigation Analysis Standard Expression).

CASE provides "*an extension of the Unified Cyber Ontology (UCO), which defines classes of cyber objects (e.g., items, tools, people, places), the relations to other cyber objects, provenance of items and actions taken in an action life-cycle. The CASE domain of discourse is focused on "investigation" concentrated on Observable Objects and their associated Facets, whereas the UCO serves as an ontological foundation for modeling the broader cyber-domain, treating observable cyber-items and their associated facets more generally. Developers of systems and tools used in cyber-investigations are working to export information in CASE format to allow automated normalization, combination, correlation, and validation of information, which means less time extracting and combining data, and more time analyzing information.*"

Figure 3 Applicability of standards to investigation process classes and activities (Source: ISO/IEC 27042:2015, Figure 1)

2. Selected Topic: Internet of Things Devices

On 27th and 28th of September 2023 in Sofia, Bulgaria WP2 organized a practitioner workshop on the topic of the Internet of Things (IoT) as a facilitator of cybercrime.

The standardisation landscape of IoT, produced by this WP2 activity, is as follows:

- ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 41, Internet of things and digital twin

This standardisation committee is responsible for the area of Internet of Things and related technologies and serves as the focus and proponent for ISO/IEC JTC 1's standardisation programme on the Internet of Things and Digital Twin, including their related technologies. Furthermore, it provides guidance to ISO/IEC JTC 1 (Information technology), IEC, ISO and other entities developing Internet of Things and Digital Twin related applications.

Of particular interest is ISO/IEC 30147:2021, *Methodology for trustworthiness of IoT system/service*, which provides system life cycle processes to implement and maintain trustworthiness in an IoT system or service by applying and supplementing ISO/IEC/IEEE 15288:2015. The system life cycle processes are applicable to IoT systems and services common to a wide range of application areas.

- ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27, Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection

This standardisation committee is responsible for the development of standards for the protection of information and ICT. This includes generic methods, techniques and guidelines to address both security and privacy aspects, such as:

- Security requirements capture methodology;
- Management of information and ICT security; in particular information security management systems, security processes, and security controls and services;
- Cryptographic and other security mechanisms, including but not limited to mechanisms for protecting the accountability, availability, integrity and confidentiality of information;
- Security management support documentation including terminology, guidelines as well as procedures for the registration of security components;
- Security aspects of identity management, biometrics and privacy;
- Conformance assessment, accreditation and auditing requirements in the area of information security management systems;
- Security evaluation criteria and methodology.

SC 27 engages in active liaison and collaboration with appropriate bodies to ensure the proper development and application of SC 27 standards and technical reports in relevant areas.

Of particular interest is its ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27/AHG 2, Security and privacy in IoT and Digital Twin and the following International Standards:

- ISO/IEC 27400:2002, *IoT security and privacy — Guidelines, providing guidelines on risks, principles and controls for security and privacy of Internet of Things (IoT) solutions.*
- ISO/IEC 27402:2023, *IoT security and privacy — Device baseline requirements, providing baseline ICT requirements for IoT devices to support security and privacy controls.*
- ISO/IEC 27403, *Guidelines for IoT-domotics², providing guidelines to analyse security and privacy risks and identifying controls that can be implemented in IoT-domotics systems.*
- ISO/IEC 27404 (under development), *Cybersecurity labelling framework for consumer IoT.*

This document defines a Universal Cybersecurity Labelling Framework for the development and implementation of cybersecurity labelling programmes for consumer IoT products and includes guidance on the following topics:

- Risks and threats associated with consumer IoT products;
- Stakeholders, roles and responsibilities;
- Relevant standards and guidance documents;
- Conformity assessment options;
- Labelling issuance and maintenance requirements; and
- Mutual recognition considerations.

The scope of this document is limited to consumer IoT products, such as IoT gateways, base stations and hubs to which multiple devices connect; smart cameras, televisions, and speakers; wearable health trackers; connected smoke detectors, door locks and window sensors; connected home automation and alarm systems, especially their gateways and hubs; connected appliances, such as washing machines and fridges; smart home assistants; and connected children's toys and baby monitors.

The Universal Cybersecurity Labelling Framework addresses the expected and intended use of IoT devices and systems by consumers, that is, the general public and non-technical users. These devices and systems are used with the understanding that the label and criteria are designed for consumer use and consumer security concerns.

Safety is not addressed in this Universal Cybersecurity Labelling Framework even though it is an important aspect to consider.

² IoT-domotics is defined as an Internet of Things (IoT) system composed of networks, devices, services and users typically used in the domicile or as electronic wearables. According to ISO/IEC TR 22417:2017, 6.3, IoT-domotics denotes the private, hence highly customizable indoor area where someone lives, alone or with friends/relatives/roommates. Thus, it includes dedicated infrastructure aimed to support those individuals, such as healthcare and wellness systems, building control systems, smart metering and systems for entertainment and gaming.

Consumer IoT devices used in an enterprise context may not be classified as consumer IoT devices due to potentially more serious implications if compromised, which then entails more stringent cybersecurity provisions.

Furthermore, in threat models of consumer IoT, there is no IT/system administrator as a pre-condition.

Products that are not intended for consumer use are excluded from this standard. Examples of excluded devices are those that are primarily intended for manufacturing, healthcare and other industrial purposes.

The Universal Cybersecurity Labelling Framework is based on requirements from international standards, with objectives to facilitate mutual recognition of labelling schemes for consumer IoT (regardless if they are binary or multi-level), avoid fragmentation of standards, eradicate duplicated testing (across countries), reduce the cost of compliance and facilitate market access for developers.

This document is applicable to consumers, developers, issuing bodies of cybersecurity labels and independent test laboratories.

- ETSI TC CYBER, Cybersecurity

Of particular interest are the following ETSI TC CYBER standardisation deliverables:

- ETSI EN 303 645:2020, *Cyber Security for Consumer Internet of Things: Baseline Requirements*,
- ETSI TR 103 621 V1.2.1;2022, *Guide to Cyber Security for Consumer Internet of Things*,
- ETSI TS 103 815 V1.1.1:2024, CYBER; *Cyber Security for Consumer Internet of Things; Requirements for Residential Smart Door Locking Devices*,
- ETSI TS 103 848 V1.1.1:2022, *Cyber Security for Home Gateways; Security Requirements as vertical from Consumer Internet of Things*,
- ETSI TS 103 701 V1.1.1:2021, CYBER; *Cyber Security for Consumer Internet of Things: Conformance Assessment of Baseline Requirements*,
- ETSI TS 103 928 V1.1.1:2023, Cyber Security (CYBER); *Cyber Security for Home Gateways; Conformance Assessment of Security Requirements as vertical from Consumer Internet of Things*,
- ETSI TR 103 743 V1.1.1:2021, CYBER; *Home Gateway Security Threat Analysis*,
- ETSI TR 103 305, *Critical Security Controls for Effective Cyber Defence (all parts, incl. Part 3: Internet of Things Sector)*.

Other Standards Development Organisations in the field of IoT are AIOTI (Alliance for Internet of Things Innovation) and W3C's Web of Things.

Partners of Task 4.2 participated in the WP2 Workshop in the area of Internet of Things (IoT) Devices and collected the following needs expressed by practitioners. These needs were assessed regarding how they can be addressed through standardisation.

- 1) **Criteria for tools** to be used when performing investigations involving IoT devices,
- 2) **Standardised data exchange format** between LEAs.

The International Standard ISO/IEC 27035, *Information technology — Information security incident management*, with its three parts can be useful for answering the needs for a **standardised data exchange format** (this implies using the CASE standard, see also Section 1).

The need for (standardised) **criteria for tools** to be used performing investigations is a general need raised in several practitioners' workshops and is treated in more detail in Subsection 3.3.1.

3. Selected Topic: Investigations involving Cloud Services

On the 22nd and 23rd of February 2023 WP2 organized a practitioner workshop on the topic of Cloud Services in the context of cybercrime in Vienna, Austria.

The standardisation landscape of Cloud Services, produced by this WP2 activity, is as follows:

ISO/IEC 22123-1:2023, *Information technology – Cloud computing - Part 1: Vocabulary*, 3.1.2 defines cloud service as one or more capabilities offered via cloud computing invoked using a defined interface. And cloud computing is defined as paradigm for enabling network access to a scalable and elastic pool of shareable physical or virtual resources with self-service provisioning and administration on-demand (ISO/IEC 22123-1:2023, 3.1.1).

Cybersecurity continues to be a significant factor in cloud computing management. Data breaches, ransomware and exposed e-mails are a few of the many ways cybercrime has wide-ranging impacts.

Despite cybersecurity professionals' best efforts, the average business cost of a data breach was 4.35 million USD in 2022³. Additionally, cybercrime impacted the global economy by 7 trillion USD³. 32% of businesses in the U.K. experienced a cyberattack in 2022³.

There are a multitude of different Cloud Services available for different purposes, each reflecting different opportunities and challenges for Law Enforcement. As the storage capability is vastly larger in cloud than in mobile devices and can be accessed from multiple units, they are frequently used for data storage as well as communications. The implications for Law Enforcement are significant as the trend is increasing for less data to be stored on devices and more to be stored remotely, reducing the digital forensic opportunities from device examinations, and increasing the need to be able to remotely access stored electronic data.

Practitioners identified the following recommendations as key priority areas for the law enforcement community:

- developing improved tools to gain access to cloud service accounts,
- a review to determine opportunities for simplifying and expediting the MLAT process, and
- training and development offer for Law Enforcement officers

as key priority areas for the law enforcement community.

3.1. State of the art in the selected topic

Applying the methodology specified in D4.1 for the area of Cloud Services, the following standardisation committees were identified together with related standardisation activities:

- ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27, *Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection*. Related standardisation deliverable:

³ <https://aag-it.com/the-latest-cyber-crime-statistics/>

- ISO/IEC 27017:2015, *Information technology - Security techniques - Code of practice for information security controls based on ISO/IEC 27002 for cloud services*⁴
- ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 38, *Cloud computing and distributed platforms*, especially the Coordination Group ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 38/CG 1 for JTC1/SC27. Related standardisation deliverable:
 - ISO/IEC 19086-4:2019 *Cloud computing - Service level agreement (SLA) framework - Part 4: Components of security and of protection of PII*⁵
- CEN/CENELEC JTC 13, *Cybersecurity and Data Protection*
- ETSI TC Cyber, *Cybersecurity*
- ETSI TC *Lawful Interception (LI)*, developing standards that support the technical requirements of national and international obligations for law enforcement, including the lawful interception and retention of the communications-related data of electronic communications. Lawful Interception (LI) and Retained Data (RD) play a crucial role in helping law enforcement agencies to investigate terrorism and serious criminal activities.

Deliverables related to investigations involving Cloud Services:

- ETSI TR 101 567 V1.1.1 (2016-01), *Cloud/Virtual Services for Lawful Interception (LI) and Retained Data (RD)*⁶
- ETSI TR 103 304 V1.1.1 (2016-07), *Personally Identifiable Information (PII) - Protection in mobile and cloud services, in particular sub-clause 6.10 Lawful Interception*⁷
- NIST SP 800-201, NIST Cloud Computing Forensic Reference Architecture⁸

This document summarizes research performed by the members of the NIST Cloud Computing Forensic Science Working Group and presents the NIST Cloud Computing Forensic Reference Architecture (CC FRA, also referred to as FRA for the sake of brevity), whose goal is to provide support for a cloud system's forensic readiness. The CC FRA is meant to help users understand which cloud forensic challenges might exist for an organization's cloud system. It identifies challenges that require at least partial mitigation strategies and how a forensic investigator would apply that to a particular forensic investigation. The CC FRA presented here is both a methodology and an initial implementation. Users are encouraged to customize this initial implementation for their specific situations and needs.

The following EU policies are related to the selected topic:

- Directive 2012/13/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 22 May 2012 on the right to information in criminal proceedings

⁴ <https://www.iso.org/standard/43757.html>

⁵ <https://www.iso.org/standard/68242.html>

⁶ https://www.etsi.org/deliver/etsi_tr/101500_101599/101567/01.01.01_60/tr_101567v010101p.pdf

⁷ https://www.etsi.org/deliver/etsi_tr/103300_103399/103304/01.01.01_60/tr_103304v010101p.pdf

⁸ <https://csrc.nist.gov/pubs/sp/800/201/ipd>

- Directive 2014/41/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 3 April 2014 regarding the European Investigation Order in criminal matters
- Directive (EU) 2016/343 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 9 March 2016 on the strengthening of certain aspects of the presumption of innocence and of the right to be present at the trial in criminal proceedings
- Directive (EU) 2016/680 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data by competent authorities for the purposes of the prevention, investigation, detection or prosecution of criminal offences or the execution of criminal penalties, and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Council Framework Decision 2008/977/JHA
- Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation)

3.2. Practitioners' needs

Partners of Task 4.2 participated in the WP2 Workshop in the area of Cloud Services and collected the following needs expressed by practitioners⁹. These needs were assessed with respect to standardisation.

- 1) Practitioners expressed the need for expediting cloud services investigations, particularly in relation to the triage of extracted cloud data, and the development of updated **tools and methods** for gaining access to Cloud Service accounts. This includes test environments, datasets, sandboxes, and standalone devices that LEAs can use to test tools and validate results.

See Subsection 3.3.1.

- 2) Practitioners expressed the need for a review of existing processes with the goal of simplifying and expediting the MLAT **process** which may lead to faster access to international cooperation.

See Subsection 3.3.2.

- 3) Practitioners expressed the need for a **framework for updating legislation**, i.e. a framework to facilitate adjusting existing legislation to take cyber considerations into account in far shorter cycles (2-3 months) than the current timeframe for introducing/amending legislation (~3 years). This would ensure that legislation keeps pace with technological advancement.

See Subsection 3.3.3.

- 4) Practitioners expressed the need for **training** and development package(s) to cyber specialists within Law Enforcement Agencies.

See Subsection 3.3.4.

⁹ The report from this Practitioners' Workshop can be downloaded from <https://backend.cyclopes-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/06/Practitioners-Gaps-and-Requirements-2nd-Public-Annual-Report-for-Industry-and-Academia.pdf>

Considering the needs expressed by practitioners in the WP2 Workshop, assessed by T4.2 and having identified those standardisation committees with which these needs can be discussed to elaborate recommendations on standardisation, the following standardisation committees were contacted by the T4.3 Lead (ASI):

- ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27, Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection
- ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 38, Cloud computing and distributed platforms
- CEN/CENELEC JTC 13, Cybersecurity and Data Protection
- ETSI TC Cyber, Cybersecurity
- ETSI TC Lawful Interception (LI)

Representatives from these standardisation committees were invited to a standardisation workshop, which was held online on 20th February 2024, in order to:

- indicate priorities regarding domains which require (further) standardisation,
- define a roadmap with recommendations for standardisation based on the needs and possibilities for the standardisation of tools, procedures and trainings related to fighting cybercrime.

13 participants, including CYCLOPES partners, joined the standardisation workshop. These included:

- Chair of ISO/IEC JTC1/SC 38, Cloud computing and distributed platforms,
- Convenor of ISO/IEC JTC1/SC 27/WG 1, Information security management systems,
- Austrian Standards International (ASI),
- Polish Platform for Homeland Security (PPHS),
- IANUS Consulting Ltd.,
- Zentrale Stelle für Informationstechnik im Sicherheitsbereich (ZITIS),
- Polismyndigheten Swedish Police Authority (SPA).

The leadership of ETSI TC LI was not able to attend the workshop but submitted written contributions.

The Chair of **ISO/IEC JTC1/SC 38** provided an overview of the work and structure of ISO/IEC JTC1/SC 38, see Figure 4.

Figure 4 Structure of ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 38

The current focus of ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 38 is on the following areas¹⁰:

- Multi-cloud & federated cloud
- Data, i.e. Dataspace, Sharing, flow, use, categories
- Digital sovereignty & organizational autonomy
- PaaS
- Trustworthiness
- Business continuity & resilience
- Edge computing

The roadmap for future work (AG5, see Figure 4) addresses the following topics:

- Cloud Computing as critical infrastructure
- Cloud Computing: Business continuity & resilience
- Sustainability of Cloud Computing
- Accountability, attestation & certification ecosystem
- Management System Standards (MSS) guidelines
- Cooperation with Open Source

The Convenor of ISO/IEC JTC1/SC 27/WG 1 presented the work and structure of **ISO/IEC JTC1/SC 27**, Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection.¹¹ A special focus was made on the conformity assessment, see Figure 5.

¹⁰ see <https://www.iso.org/committee/601355/x/catalogue/p/0/u/1/w/0/d/0>

¹¹ <https://www.iso.org/committee/45306.html>

CONFORMITY ASSESSMENT builds trust, confidence and assurance

Figure 5 Conformity assessment in the framework of ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27

3.3. Recommendations on standardisation

3.3.1. Tools

The need for having standardised criteria (requirements) for automated tools being capable of merging large datasets from multiple providers with varying proprietary formats and targeting key data of interest for investigations, were discussed and confirmed during the workshop. In addition, it was suggested that similar (standardised) criteria for tools and methods to identify user login credentials, and to by-pass passwords, biometrics and multi factor authentication, would be beneficial for LEAs and laboratories performing digital forensics.

It was noted that in CWA 17865:2022¹², *Requirements and Guidelines for a complete end-to-end mobile forensic investigation chain*, references are made to investigations involving cloud services:

7.9.4 ... *In many mobile devices, some of the user data is stored on cloud servers or physically separated from the device itself. It shall be ensured that this data is acquired appropriately too, if legally permissible and feasible. If backups of the device are legally available and accessible on cloud servers or external storage these should also be acquired.*

8.3.2 Criteria to be met when accessing messages, cloud and sensitive documents.

Suitable criteria shall be set up for accessing messages, cloud data, and sensitive documents so that the right to privacy is protected and all the guarantees are in place to make sure that no excessive and disproportionate amount of private data is processed. In addition to defining the threshold for when to access these documents at

¹² https://www.cencenelec.eu/media/CEN-CENELEC/CWAs/RI/cwa17865_2022.pdf

all in the first place, appropriate limits shall be defined to the specific data that can be retrieved, accessed and analysed in the first place, and then included as part of the trial proceedings. Recent case law establishes that retrieval of data by the relevant authorities is to be executed only upon written request and on the respective national/ local legal basis. To collect the requested information, the requirement of necessity shall first be fulfilled, which means that there shall be ground for initial suspicion for the offence. Furthermore, the specific type of crime needs to be taken into account as well, as additional limitations, such as obtaining a specific court order, may need to be overcome beforehand.

With regards to limiting the amount of data, the extraction of data shall also be proportional and as granular as possible, that is, not to allow for a bulk extraction of all data but only for specific information, relevant to the case. Granularity can be expressed by only obtaining certain types of data, only acquiring certain sources (e.g. devices, accounts) or limiting the acquisition to a given time frame.

This could be a first step to define standardised criteria for digital forensics tools. The chair of ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 38 suggested that, before submitting a proposal for starting with the elaboration of a new standard, this need should be discussed first with cloud service providers; the ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 38/AG 5, Long-term strategy, could serve as a forum for such a discussion.

In the context of criteria for tools the need for their reliable testing was discussed in order to enable LEAs to test the tools and to assess tools provided by different vendors.

This can be addressed in a standard specifying the criteria/requirements of tools and defining the test procedures to verify that the tool(s) meet the requirements. Based on that this can be used for conformity assessment purposes, e.g. the vendor can issue a self-declaration or involves a certification body for issuing a certificate for the tool, see Figure 5.

Such a recommended standardisation activity should take into account the work performed by the NIST Computer Forensics Tool Testing Program (CFTT). The goal of CFTT is to establish a methodology for testing computer forensic software tools by development of general tool specifications, test procedures, test criteria, test sets, and test hardware. The results provide the information necessary for toolmakers to improve tools, for users to make informed choices about acquiring and using computer forensics tools, and for interested parties to understand the tools capabilities.¹³

Another but European organisation is the European Anti-Cybercrime Technology Development Association (EACTDA)¹⁴ which purpose is the development of technological solutions for European Law Enforcement Agencies and Forensic Laboratories to use them in their fight against crime. Members of the Association are European Law Enforcement Agencies, ministries of interior, forensic institutes, and other European public security practitioners as well as relevant research technology organisations and industrial partners.

In additions the activities and results of EU-funded research projects like LAGO (Lessen Data Access and Governance Obstacles)¹⁵ should be taken into account.

LEAs participating in the workshop raised the need that similar to NIST a new European body available for tool testing should be created.

¹³ <https://www.nist.gov/itl/ssd/software-quality-group/computer-forensics-tool-testing-program-cftt>

¹⁴ <https://www.eactda.eu/>

¹⁵ <https://lago-europe.eu/>

3.3.2. Process

A mutual legal assistance treaty (MLAT) is an agreement between two or more countries for the purpose of gathering and exchanging information in an effort to enforce public or criminal laws. A mutual legal assistance request is commonly used to formally interrogate a suspect in a criminal case, when the suspect resides in a foreign country.

Examples of MLATs are:

- Convention on Mutual Administrative Assistance in Tax Matters,
- European Convention on Information on Foreign Law,
- European Convention on Mutual Assistance in Criminal Matters,
- European Convention on the International Validity of Criminal Judgments,
- Inter-American Convention on Mutual Assistance in Criminal Matters,
- United Nations Convention against Transnational Organized Crime,
- Ljubljana-The Hague Convention on Mutual Legal Assistance (regarding international criminal law).

Practitioners suggested that the mutual legal assistance treaty process should be reviewed to determine opportunities for simplifying and expediting the MLAT process, including the introduction of time limits and making use of opportunities for automation.

In this context, LEAs raised the need for a uniformed reporting template for data to be disclosed when they issue a MLAT subpoena to Cloud service providers.

These needs can be met with the revision of ISO/IEC 27037:2012, *Security techniques - Guidelines for identification, collection, acquisition and preservation of digital evidence*. This edition from 2012 doesn't cover investigations involving cloud services. The ISO/IEC standard would benefit from being revised and updated to reflect current and state-of-the-art technologies, processes, and procedures; e.g. detailing how to properly secure cloud data, label it and protect it from change.

ISO/IEC 27037:2012 was even subject to a systematic review in 2023 and the interim result shows that the standard was confirmed. In the standardisation workshop it was concluded that a proposal for a revision of the ISO/IEC 27037 should be developed and submitted to ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27. CYCLOPES partners participating in this ISO Committee (see Figure 2) supported the recommendation and the Convenor of ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27/WG 1 stated that he will address this in one of the next Working Group meetings.

3.3.3. Legal Framework

Law enforcement agencies reported that the legal framework cannot keep pace with rapidly evolving cybercrime, including cloud services. A framework is needed to expedite the updating of legislation, enabling the integration of cyber considerations into existing laws much more swiftly than the current process allows for the introduction or amendment of legislation.

A public consultation meeting of the High-Level Group (HLG) on access to data for effective law enforcement respecting ethics and fundamental rights protection, especially to privacy and data protection, was held online¹⁶ at the same time as the standardisation workshop.

The participants of the CYCLOPES standardisation workshop concluded that this need for a legal framework is not in the sphere of influence of (voluntary) standardisation and should be addressed at an appropriate level.

3.3.4. Training

Law enforcement authorities confirmed that training and development opportunities for law enforcement officers are critical to successfully combating cybercrime.

Research projects like FORMOBILE¹⁷ developed dedicated forensic training programmes, incl. a specialised workshop for forensic laboratories. The European Cybercrime Training and Education Group (ECTEG)¹⁸ built on the foundations of the work completed in FORMOBILE through its dedicated project MobiFor.

In ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27 the competency of personnel are subject to standardisation (see Figure 5):

- ISO/IEC 27021:2017, *Information technology — Security techniques — Competence requirements for information security management systems professionals*
- ISO/IEC 19896-1, *Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection — Requirements for the competence of IT security conformance assessment body personnel — Part 1: Introduction, concepts and general requirements*
- ISO/IEC 19896-2, *Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection — Requirements for the competence of IT security conformance assessment body personnel — Part 2: Knowledge and skills requirements for ISO/IEC 19790 testers and validators*
- ISO/IEC 19896-3, *Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection — Requirements for the competence of IT security conformance assessment body personnel — Part 3: Knowledge and skills requirements for ISO/IEC 15408 evaluators and certifiers*
- ISO/IEC TR 27109, *Cybersecurity education and training*

Based on the required competencies training programmes can be derived.

3.4. List of stakeholders

In the area of Cloud services, the following stakeholders were identified:

- National LEAs,
- Europol,

¹⁶ https://home-affairs.ec.europa.eu/whats-new/events/public-consultation-meeting-high-level-group-hlg-access-data-effective-law-enforcement-2024-02-20_en

¹⁷ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/832800>

¹⁸ <https://www.ecteg.eu/>

- The European Network of Law Enforcement Technology Services (ENLETS),
- EU Agency for law enforcement training (CEPOL),
- EC DG HOME,
- EC DG JUST,
- Interpol,
- Forensic laboratories,
- Forensic tool vendors,
- Legal and ethical advisors,
- Prosecutors,
- Defence attorneys,
- Judges,
- Ministries of justice,
- Cloud Service providers.

4. Follow-up of and update for recommendations from previous reporting periods

In Deliverable D4.3, Section 3 the topic of “**Automotive Digital Forensics**” was analysed in more detail, especially the need for the standardisation of system architectures and vehicle data ports.

As recommended in D4.3, Section 3.3.1, this need was addressed by ETSI TC LI and led to the ETSI Technical Specification ETSI TS 103 976, *LEA support services; Interface for Lawful Disclosure of vehicle-related data*¹⁹. This ETSI Technical Specification was published in February 2024 and defines an interface between two parties to make lawful requests for data relating to vehicles, and to respond to those requests where appropriate. The usage of the interface does not jeopardise the safety and security of the vehicles involved and takes into account the boundaries of the responsibilities of the parties involved.

ETSI TS 103 976 was supported by the following parties²⁰: Ministère de l'Intérieur, Volkswagen AG, PIDS, OTD, BfV, Public Safety Canada, UTIMACO TS GmbH, AREA Spa, National Technical Assistance, Attorney-General's Department, Bayerisches Landeskriminalamt, Tencastle Limited, iTrust Ethics Ltd, BKA, Ministère Economie et Finances, LKA Niedersachsen, ZITiS, umlaut, PFA. As can be seen in this list of supporting organisations, partners from CYCLOPES were involved.

Next to that CYCLOPES established the Automotive Digital Forensics (ADF) Group in 2022 to follow up and continue working in the area of automotive digital forensics. The ambition was to create a stronger connection between law enforcement agencies (LEAs), experts with a high-level experience and innovative technologies. ASI participated in the ADF group and provided advice on how to contribute to standardisation to address gaps in the standardisation landscape identified during the work of the group, e.g. elaborating a New Work Item Proposal.

Conclusion

There are some standards which fully address the needs expressed by practitioners. Considering the fast-evolving technological developments and to keep track of evolving cybercrime techniques, it seems that some standards need to be reviewed and revised, e.g. ETSI TR 101 567 V1.1.1 (2016-01), ETSI TR 103 304 V1.1.1 (2016-07) and in particular ISO/IEC 27037:2012.

Standard(s) for specifying criteria and requirements of tools to be used in investigations (digital forensics) involving Cloud services are needed to enable trustworthy selection of such tools. To verify the compliance of tools with the criteria/requirements, functional test methods are also required, and these can be also subject to standardisation.

¹⁹ https://www.etsi.org/deliver/etsi_ts/103900_103999/103976/01.01.01_60/ts_103976v010101p.pdf

²⁰ https://portal.etsi.org/webapp/workprogram/Report_WorkItem.asp?WKI_ID=68753

Annex A: Standardisation overview

In ISO/IEC Guide 2:2004²¹, 1.1 standardisation is defined as an activity of establishing, with regard to actual or potential problems, provisions for common and repeated use, aimed at the achievement of the optimum degree of order in a given context. Important benefits of standardisation are improvement of the suitability of products, processes and services for their intended purposes, prevention of barriers to trade and facilitation of technological cooperation. Standardisation supports the social and economic development by ensuring safety, quality and competitiveness of products, services, and processes on various levels (e. g. performance, composition, interoperability, applicability and many more). This in turn supports economic activity of businesses of all sizes and allows them access markets all over the world.

Standardisation is governed by the principles of consensus, openness, inclusiveness transparency, national commitment and coherence as outlined in the Agreement on Technical Barriers to Trade of the World Trade Organisation (WTO TBT Agreement) and in Regulation (EU) No 1025/2012 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 October 2012 on European standardisation.

The output of standardisation are standards. According to ISO/IEC Guide 2:2004, 3.1 a standard is a document, established by consensus and approved by a recognized body, that provides, for common and repeated use, rules, guidelines or characteristics for activities or their results, aimed at the achievement of the optimum degree of order in a given context. Standards are voluntary in their application and should be based on the consolidated results of science, technology, and experience, and aimed at the promotion of optimum community benefits. Standards are initiated and drafted by stakeholders such as industry, incl. SMEs, public authorities, research organisations, societal and environmental stakeholders, consumer organisations, trade unions and conformity assessment bodies.

There are numerous organizations developing standards, ranging from companies, consortia and industry in the private sector, to national, regional and international organizations. The latter three constitute the bulk of the international standardisation system, required by the WTO TBT Agreement to follow its principles and requirements for standards development. There are also NGOs with specific socio-economic or environmental goals that develop and publish standards.

National Standardisation Bodies (NSB) are standardisation organizations located in each country. They bridge the local communities with groups of relevant stakeholders outside of their country and represent the pillars of the European and International standardisation. Being member of European Standardisation Organisations NSBs are obliged to implement European Standards as national standards and withdraw any conflicting national standards.

The European standardisation activities are conducted within the European Committee for Standardisation (CEN), the European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardisation (CENELEC), and the European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI).

CEN brings together the national standardisation bodies of 34 European countries and provides a platform for standardisation in various areas, including products, materials, services, and processes. CENELEC ensures standardisation in the electro-technical

²¹ ISO/IEC Guide 2:2004, Standardization and related activities — General vocabulary, is adopted in Europe as European Standard EN 45020:2006.

engineering field, and ETSI produces standards for information and communications technology.

The network of European standardisation includes more than 200.000 experts from different countries and from the different stakeholders, i. e. business, industry and commerce, service providers, consumers, environmental and societal organisations, public authorities, and regulators, as well as other public and private institutions. The European Standardisation Organisations aim to support needs of the market and of different stakeholders, promoting the European Standardisation System and leading the implementation of best practice in standardisation around the world. They collaborate with key stakeholders' organisations at national, European and international level, support international Standardisation and cooperate closely with international Standardisation Organisation such as ISO and IEC. Participation in European Standardisation follows the national delegation principle, i. e. national members (NSB, NC) host national committees populated with national stakeholders and these national committees contribute to the elaboration of European Standards.

International standardisation activities are conducted at three major international Standardisation Organisation: International Organization for Standardisation (ISO), International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC) and International Telecommunication Union (ITU).

ISO is an independent international organization that includes 165 national standards bodies as its members. International standards, produced by ISO, cover a wide variety of areas and represent consensus of experts from many countries. All CEN members are also members of ISO.

Members of IEC are 89 National Committees, represented by delegates from industry, research and government bodies of each country. IEC produces standards covering all aspects of production and use of electrical and electronic devices and systems. All CENELEC members are also members of IEC.

CEN and CENELEC have dedicated agreements with the International Organization for Standardisation (ISO) and the International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC), promoting the benefits of the international standards to international trade and markets harmonization. The high level of convergence between the European and international standards is facilitated by the ongoing technical cooperation between CEN and ISO (Vienna Agreement) and between CENELEC and IEC (Frankfurt Agreement). The main objectives of these agreements are to provide a:

- framework for the optimal use of resources and expertise available for standardisation work;
- mechanism for information exchange between international and European Standardisation Organizations to increase the transparency of ongoing work at international and European levels.

International Standards from ISO and IEC following the Vienna or Frankfurt Agreement become the status of European Standards (designation EN ISO, EN ISO/IEC, EN IEC).

ITU is an inter-governmental organization belonging to the United Nations and develops technical standards that facilitate the use of public telecommunication services and systems for communications in the area of ICT. Its membership comprises nearly 200 countries and almost 800 private-sector entities and academic institutions.

Participation in International Standardisation of ISO and IEC follows the national delegation principle, i. e. national members (NSB, NC) host national committees populated with national stakeholders and these national committees contribute to the elaboration of International Standards.

A vast array of normative documents is classed under the generic label of "private standards". Generally, a normative document developed and published by an organization outside of the recognized standards development organizations at national, regional, or international level is considered to be a private standard. There is not only a vast range of private standards (and growing in number), but there are also significant differences between the bodies and organizations that develop these standards related to such aspects as governance, development approach, stakeholder engagement, transparency, and consensus.

Some of these Private Standards Development Organisations liaise with recognized standards development organizations. Such examples are IEEE and ENISA liaising with ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27, Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection or OASIS liaising with ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 37/WG 2, Biometric technical interfaces. Some specifications from Private Standards Development Organisations were provided by them to recognized standards development organizations to be implemented as standards.

Another aspect to consider is how standardisation bodies deal with intellectual property in standards. In many sectors of the economy, companies make significant financial and human investments in the development of new technologies and products. As a result, the best available technology that experts want to include in a standard is often protected by one or more patents. This is especially true in certain areas where interoperable and complex technologies cause standard developers to consider new and emerging technologies that are normally protected by patents. These contributions may contain patented technologies which are commonly known as Standard Essential Patents (SEP). When it is not possible on technical grounds to make or operate equipment or methods which comply with a standard without infringing a SEP, i. e. without using technologies that are covered by one or more patents, the patent is described as being 'essential' for the application of the standard. To preserve the universal approach of standards, while also respecting the rights of the patent holders, ISO, IEC, ITU, CEN, CENELEC and ETSI have developed an intellectual property rights (IPR) policy. In brief, this policy encourages the early disclosure and identification of patents that may relate to standards under development. The IPR Policy provides for the incorporation of patented technology into new standards, on condition that the IPR holder is ready to allow this either without financial compensation or at Fair, Reasonable and non-Discriminatory (FRAND) conditions to other standard users.

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